

COMPOSITE STRUCTURES FOR COMMERCIAL TRANSPORT AIRCRAFT

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The National Aeronautics and Space Administration has established an Aircraft Energy Efficiency (ACEE) program with the objective of refining and demonstrating, in operational and production environments, technological improvements in aerodynamics, structures, and electronics that can significantly improve the fuel efficiency of future transport aircraft.

This paper will describe the portion of ACEE program directed toward the advancement of composite structures technology. The specific objective of the ACEE composites program is to provide the technology and confidence that will enable commercial transport manufacturers to commit to extensive use of composites in their future production aircraft.

Contractual programs have been established with the three principal U.S. transport aircraft manufacturers, The Boeing Company, Lockheed Aircraft Corporation and McDonnell Douglas Corporation. Each company will develop two composite components. One component will be a representative piece of secondary structure. The other component will be a medium-sized primary structure.

The programs are expected to demonstrate the weight savings that are achievable in commercial aircraft structure. Just as important, however, is the need to develop and demonstrate manufacturing techniques that are suited to the economically sound production of composite structure. The manufacturing approach being employed to construct the components will be described in the paper. A brief summary of the components and some of their design features follows.

The DC-10 upper aft rudder consists of an all composite structure with only metal hinge fittings and conductive straps for lightning protection. The main box structure is graphite/epoxy. The box is about four meters long with an average chord of about 60 cm. The box is molded as a single cocurred assembly that utilizes expanded rubber tooling. The box structure weighs about half as much as the aluminum rudder.

The L-1011 composite aileron is still in its early design stage, but indications are this part will weigh about 25% less than the metal aileron and require only about one fifth the number of parts. The aileron is about 2.5

meters long and 1.2 meters in chord. In contrast to the other secondary components being developed under this program, the aileron is located in a strong acoustic field and is subject to foreign object impact from runway debris.

The third, and heaviest, secondary structure component being developed as a composite structure is the Boeing 727 elevator. The elevator is 5.8 meters long with a chord of about one meter. The component is mass balanced and, therefore, component weight reduction is enhanced by a substantial reduction in balance weight requirements.

The present design for the composite L-1011 vertical fin will be shown. The fin has a span of 7.6 meters and a root chord of about 2.7 meters. The component is essentially all graphite/epoxy except for aluminum truss members in the lower ribs.

The Boeing 737 horizontal stabilizer has about the same area as the 727 elevator. The composite design will require far fewer parts than the existing aluminum design and a corresponding reduction in fasteners. Since part count and fastener count greatly influence manufacturing and assembly labor costs, the composite tail should be more economical to produce than the metal tail.

The vertical tail for the Douglas DC-10 is about the same size as the L-1011 tail. However, the construction details are very different. The DC-10 tail is a four-spar structure and the skin is interrupted by several cut outs. The redesigned box structure is expected to show a weight saving of over 20%.

The components described above all show significant weight savings, but in total they represent only a modest percentage of the aircraft structural weight. Comparable weight savings must be achieved for large primary structure as well. Therefore, the ACEE composites program also includes the development of technology for wing structures. The wing program is time-phased to make maximum use of information and technology developed in the components program. The program for the development of composite wing structure is still in its formative stages, but the status and current plans will be discussed in the presentation.